

Significance of the Smartphone in Pastoral Ministry

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Abstract

Ways through which things are done today has significantly changed. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has introduced innovations significant changes in this direction. This paper hinges on the use of the modern technological device popularly known as the smartphone. This narrows the study to the use of opportunities such as Goggle apps, social media, functions of smartphones and challenges and solutions on its use. It is worth noting that the Christian ministry has taken a new shape through the use of these applications on the smartphone. However, people in recent times have used the smartphone to do bad contrary to the purpose for which it was invented. A good example is in the area some youths have duped innocent ones through the smartphone. Surprisingly, some ministers of the Gospel have also fallen into this group of indecent users of the smartphone. The paper aims at promoting the positive results of the smartphone in the ministry to reach out to both the saved and lost souls to the glory of God.

Keywords: Maximizing, Smartphone, Christian, Church, Ministries

Introduction

The year 2020 witnessed a global pandemic called COVID -19. For almost half of the year, different organisations, institutions and even countries devised various means to regulate public gatherings as the disease was said to spread through contact. This resulted in a total “lock down” of movement worldwide. Consequently, churches could not meet for programmes as this was prohibited by law. One fact is that the Word of God cannot remain static. Therefore, each church had to devise a different approach through which they could disseminate the Word of God. One way was the use of the print and electronic media. Hence, the internet and social media became avenues of reaching out to God’s people.

The Church in recent years has used the Internet and social media in the course of spreading the good news to the lost world. However, there has been a slow move in the judicious use of this avenue. Churches and Christian entrepreneurs now own newspaper outfits as well as radio and television stations which are all geared at spreading the Gospel. With the advent of satellite television service, some churches have established their own satellite television stations, which have proved useful as a means of hosting worship services and Bible studies. However, what was new from the COVID-19 experience was the realisation of the possibilities and power of the internet and social media. With the restriction of movement around the world, every interaction, meeting, education avenue, worship and indeed life itself moved online. The internet and social media became the arena for worship services, Bible studies, evangelism, fellowship and other forms of church ministry.

In 2008, Barack Obama ran a successful political campaign driven by the use of social media. Donald Trump, on the other hand, used his Twitter account as an effective instrument in his contest for U.S. presidency and has used it since then as an instrument of governance.¹ Several smart entrepreneurs have floated whole businesses based online and have made huge successes out of it. The Nigerian church was largely absent online

until the outbreak of COVID. Every field of life has been forced to adjust to the changes brought by the advancement of ICT gadgets. Christian ministry has also taken a new shape in the 21st century because of the advancement of Information and Communication Technology. There is no doubt that the more technological advancement is promoted, the easier it is to communicate with humans in the world. The paper concentrates on available opportunities through which the smartphones is used to the glory of God in the ministry including Google and other social media gadgets.

For proper understanding of this paper, the key terms are briefly explained. Maximizing means the greatest possible degree or level of ability one can attain in utilising something in a more productivity way or manner. Smartphone refers to a mobile electronic device or telephone with highly advanced features, capable of sending text messages. It was introduced by IBM (International Business Machinery) and expanded to include companies like Apple and Samsung. A Christian is someone who has professed Christ as his Saviour and Lord, striving daily to live like Christ (cf. John 1:9). Church refers to a gathering of saved persons while Ministries refers to all areas of Christian activities in the church.

Opportunities through Smartphones for Christian and Church Ministries

Several ways abound through which the smartphone can be used to spread the gospel message. These are done through several means such as videos, audio/podcasts, texts, and animations. While some of these applications are free, others are paid versions.

Several applications are accessible on Google account on all smartphones. Christians have opportunity to use these devices to help them grow in the Lord and do ministry through the available apps. These are explored through a number of applications such as: E-mail account, Google Calendar, Google map, Contact list, etc. Gmail is one of the world's most widely-used web email service. It is used via the smartphone, synchronised with multiple other devices. The inbox is accessed anywhere as long as there is an internet connection. It is used to communicate with people worldwide, including church members and non-church members; it is an electronic form of posting a letter.

Google Calendar is a web-based calendar used via smartphones and enables users to keep track of important events and coordinate meetings. It can be integrated into Gmail, contacts, and even Google Drive, functioning as a diary enabling one to keep a reminder of events and appointments. Google Map, a web mapping facility, offers users satellite imagery, aerial shooting, and directions. Transit-Google maps offers route planner, allowing users to find available guides as they drive, walk or ride bikes.² This application makes it easier for users to detect unfamiliar places they travel to without much guidance.

Contact list application allows users to store and unify contact information about the people they communicate with on phone and access same through other gadgets. Google contact allows inputting basic information about a person's name, email address, nickname, title, phone number, and other details about him/her. It provides further information like their employer, department, and even job title. Google contacts list helps to keep information about people even when the phone is changed or lost. Saving the contacts into the Google contacts helps one to obtain such contacts using other ICT gadgets.

Google Play is an application that helps to give access to an individual's favourite apps, games, movies, television shows, books, music, news, and magazines in one place, which can be downloaded for offline and online use. Google Drive is a storage source of files and folders of different natures. Each file saved therein can be downloaded and used anywhere. Such files can also be shared with others. Hangouts Chat/Google Meets provide opportunities to have a video conference call with church members and other people, enables group meeting interactions helpful in discipleship and other functional meetings. Google News provides an opportunity to access both local and international news. YouTube enables users to upload, download vides and watch same later. Google Photos is an avenue to store and share photos on the phone for future use. A backup helps to retrieve photos lost on the phone.

Other opportunities avail for ministry improvement in the church through the use of the phone. Some of these include: WhatsApp, a platform for interacting with other users and making calls, either in audio or video formats. WhatsApp uses the internet to send and receive messages, images, audio or videos through the Internet to communicate and significantly reduce cost. Telegram is similar to WhatsApp. However, it has more advanced features. The group video in Telegram can be stored for future use, and the screen can be shared with other group members via streaming. Historical information can be kept for prospective group members; it has unlimited server storage, among other benefits. Group members can be up to 200,000, and users can send large files on it, unlike WhatsApp messenger.

Facebook is a good platform for updating status, sharing content, and making calls. It has a live-streaming option too. Twitter is a service that enables one to receive news and follow friends and celebrities. It is used to post short messages and share photos, videos, texts and links to followers. Tweets are assigned to the user's profile and/or sent his followers. These can be accessed on Twitter search. The Christian community can use Twitter to reach several people, advertise programmes and even do publicity for the church and her ministries. Instagram is an application used to share a user's best photos with his followers and interact or/and engage with influencers. It is a popular photo-sharing app with over one billion active users. It can be used for ministry purposes in reaching out to some church members that have interest in the app via smartphone. Tiktok, another application, allows for short video sharing. Church leaders and followers can use this application to put through short, fascinating drama to reach millions of souls.

Other Functions of Smartphones and Apps

There are other functions of Smartphones and apps that may help in Christian ministry. Among these are: Zoom, a video conference application used to reach people. Skype is an application used via smartphones and computers to make calls. It is an entirely free option for a call. English and Bible dictionaries can be downloaded and accessed to check the meaning of Biblical names and English words. Hymns and Bible applications provide opportunities to read the Bible and sing hymns without stress. Reading the Bible can be part of the Bible apps and can be used for evangelism purposes.

There is also Notepad for keeping notes for future use. Audio recorders are used to keep sensitive interrogations for reference options while keeping records of interactions through their smartphones. They can also use it like Mp3 for recording sermons. Video recorder also used to keep audio-visual portions of a sermon or service. Other features available through smartphones, including alarm notifications, mini lighting and torches, calculators, source of information like FM radio, document scanners, and many more.

Challenges and Solutions of Maximizing Smartphones for Ministry

It is expedient to first discuss the challenges before the solutions. Every endeavour in life is often faced with challenges. There also challenges involved in the use of the smartphone for the ministry. To begin with, it is important to note that some Christian and the church leaders desire to use ICT gadgets for ministry, but face some challenges. The challenges include:

Digital Illiteracy: The low level of understanding of the use of the smartphone among our young ones has resulted in addiction. Some of these young ones have engaged in activities detrimental to the purpose for which the facility was invented. A good example is that today, students have turned to the use of the phone to perform examination malpractices instead of studying hard.³ Some others have taken to the download of some applications which teach them sin. Some have become addicted to pornographic activities leading to early sex, sex outside the matrimonial home and/or fornication. The Internet which is a great tool to reach out to the world has become a weapon Satan uses to catch the young ones. Some young ones also engage in evil advertisements and distracting applications such as 'games' through which they waste their precious time instead of surfing the gain information related to their studies. Students have used some of such distracting applications to draw together cliques with evil intents (robbery gangs, cult groups, etc.).

Network and Signal Strength: The challenges to the full utilisation of the online media in Nigeria and many parts of Africa range from unstable electricity supply, lack of internet coverage and slow speed where available, high cost of data, to unavailability of proper gadgets for many people. Also, some live in remote areas where the network signal is poor or unavailable. It jeopardises the desire to involve in online evangelism and discourages several pastors from investing in online evangelism or ministry.⁴

Phone Storage Capacity: Low phone storage capacities of some smartphones cannot support the storage of large files. This hinders the desire to keep files for future use and may cause one to lose several essential files. Some pastors desire to purchase the needed gadget, but lack the financial capability. This naturally kills their morale. Some of the suggested solutions to the above-mentioned challenges will be of great assistance to the current generation minister of the gospel who intends to make inroads into the ministry. The serious Christian and minister should determine to be digitally literate and should therefore consciously put in effort required. This calls for training or learning from the younger generation or colleagues. The Church should constantly organise workshops centred on computer literacy to help her members and ministers.

Discipline: The importance of this paper cannot be overemphasised. Ministers of the Gospel, especially the young ones should learn to discipline themselves in relation to the use of technological devices. This aspect spreads among many things: avoiding high volume of PA systems in the church which brings distractions in the premises. Maintaining decorum during the service promotes discipline in the church. Making rules against distraction in the church can help in this direction. Periodically preaching against activities such as pornography, internet fraud, gangs will discourage young ones who may have been attracted to such distractions will go a long way to reducing if not totally eradicate their interests in such evil ways. There should be restrictions in the church regarding the use of smartphones during worship hours. That will serve as a measure to avoid distractions. Christians should be encouraged to make better use of the smartphone in relation to the ministry. The Church should be a model in maintaining discipline regarding use of smartphones.

No doubt, some members of our churches are deficient in the use of the smartphone. Such church can enroll in business centres to learn applications such as XShare,” “Xender,” “Bluetooth,” “Infrared,” and other Applications used to send and receive videos, audios, songs, and many other information. Previously downloaded Christian films, songs, and even cartoons for children were shared with church members via the non-internet-based Apps. Ministers in this dispensation should be encouraged to take advantage of the Internet as a forum to spread the good news of Jesus Christ. They should work towards improving their skills regarding the use of the smartphone as a means to enhancing the ministry mandate. The contemporary minister should build interest in the use of the smartphone working towards to exploring the applications that promote the ministry mandate. This will enable him use such related applications to reach the world for Christ. The minister today should be conversant with platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and use them as marketing tools for publishing the gospel.⁵

Creating special interest in the internet provides an avenue for the minister to serve as a digital missionary. Skills developed through this exploration enables him present the Gospel more attractively to the lost world. He should also work towards using the media as a forum for gospel propagation.⁶ The world today is more interested in clips and audios than physical presentation. The minister in being able to present the gospel in the social media enables him reach a wider audience and listeners than doing the job in a stagnated environment.⁷ The Lord’s work is done in a better enhanced way this way.⁸

Today’s minister should thirst to be a web specialist as this helps him reach out to people of different races, tribes and countries online. Online classes in both Bible study and discipleship will go a long way to win souls to Christ. Follow up can be done online leading to the growth of the Church.⁹ No doubt, Information and Communication Technology has provided numerous opportunities for virtual contacts and electronic meetings for church programmes today through the use of applications such as Facebook, WhatsApp and other audio-video applications. Such avenues have also been used for worship services and other church related meetings. This

avenue was explored during the COVID 19 pandemic when there was a ban on public gatherings and meetings in 2021. These means became suitable alternative avenues for worship against physical church worship service.¹⁰

Evangelistic activities have become more pronounced through virtual churches where more people have access to participate in worship or teachings of the Word of God, thus promoting missions. This is a great opportunity to reaching out to the virtual world. Cyber missions recently have evolved and focused on reaching the unreached people groups in the virtual world. The validity of church ministry and missions for the 21st century significantly depends on the skill of church digital communications. The COVID-19 pandemic lockdown measure proved him right, particularly in cosmopolitan areas for urban missions.¹¹

The church has grown as individuals, families, and small groups gather around electronic devices to listen to teachings from the Bible or to participate in worship experience. During the COVID 19 lockdown, social ministries organised through virtual churches made it possible for some churches to reach out to people. For instance, through the social media, a virtual church raised some amount of money through electronic transfers to help people who were in need of foodstuffs, and similar essentials through the same means. Thus, the Church could continue meeting its obligations of missions through the use of mass media and social media tools including radio, television, cable TV networks for evangelism and disseminate information as valuable means of carrying out church missions mandate during the COVID-19 pandemic.¹² It is necessary for the Christian who desires to grow in the Spirit to possess a smartphone as this gadget will help him know what he did not know before and help him in Christian discipleship. Several other advantages abound regarding the use of the smartphone.

Conclusion

This paper has explored how the smartphone can be used to promote the Gospel of Christ in this dispensation. The paper also discussed the opportunities available through the use of the smartphone for Christian and Church ministries, challenges and solutions of maximising smartphones for ministries and using smartphones for online ministries. The Church should consciously take bold steps and reposition herself to use smartphones at their reach to do ministry. The minister is required to put in the effort required to master the use of smartphones for ministry. Every gospel minister should learn to use the smartphone for ministry.

Endnotes

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¹¹Adejuwon, 159.

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